

Studies on Formation of 3-Arylidene-flavanones in Alkaline Medium

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Among the 2-hydroxyacetophenones (2a-e) only 2a bearing a 5-OH group has been found to form 3-arylidene-flavanones during condensation with aromatic aldehydes in alkaline medium. The observed inability of 2b and 2c in this respect contradicts the findings of several recent reports. Moreover, the ^1H nmr spectral data of the alleged 3-arylidene-flavanones do not correspond to those for any geometrical isomer of these compounds.

3-Arylidene-flavanones, also known as flavinogenides, are formed by condensation of flavanones with aromatic aldehydes. The use of acids for effecting this condensation is long known^{1,2} while the use of organic bases like pyridine³ and piperidine⁴ has appeared in the literature subsequently. First Seikel *et al.*⁵ and then Shah and Shah⁶ reported the formation of a 3-arylidene-flavanone in alkaline medium through the isolation of 6-hydroxy-3-benzylidene-flavanone (1a) during the condensation of 2,5-dihydroxyacetophenone (2a) with benzaldehyde. However, none of these two groups assigned the configuration of the double bond in 1a. Keane *et al.*⁷ first determined the stereochemistry of 3-arylidene-flavanones by synthesising the isomeric *E* and *Z* compounds and studying their ^1H nmr spectral data. Recently, Chawla and Sharma⁸⁻¹⁰ have reported the formation of seven 3-arylidene-flavanones of undetermined configuration by condensing the 2-hydroxyacetophenones (2a-c) with aromatic aldehydes in alkaline medium. In connection with our studies on nickel peroxide oxidation of 2'-hydroxychalcones and flavanones¹¹ we carried out Claisen-Schmidt reaction involving 2-hydroxyacetophenone (2b) and several aromatic aldehydes, but in none of these cases we could isolate a 3-arylidene-flavanone. Moreover, an examination of the ^1H nmr spectral data reported by Chawla and Sharma^{8,9} for 3-arylidene-flavanones, revealed that these differed from the data for both *E*- and *Z*-isomers of this class of compounds reported by other groups^{7,12}. These apparent deviations led us to undertake a systematic investigation of the condensation reactions of 2-hydroxyacetophenones and flavanones with aromatic aldehydes and to study the ^1H nmr spectral features of the 3-arylidene-flavanones formed.

The experimental procedure reported by Chawla and Sharma^{8,9} was first followed by taking the 2-hydroxyacetophenones (2b and 2c) and the aromatic aldehydes, benzaldehyde, *p*-anisaldehyde and *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde. However, 3-arylidene-flavanone was not obtained in any one of these

a ; $\text{R}^1 = \text{OH}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{R}^3 = \text{H}$ b ; $\text{R}^1 = \text{OH}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}^3 = \text{OMe}$
c ; $\text{R}^1 = \text{R}^2 = \text{R}^3 = \text{H}$ d ; $\text{R}^1 = \text{R}^2 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}^3 = \text{OMe}$
e ; $\text{R}^1 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{OMe}$, $\text{R}^3 = \text{Cl}$ f ; $\text{R}^1 = \text{NO}_2$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{R}^3 = \text{H}$

2a ; $\text{R}^1 = \text{OH}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{H}$
b ; $\text{R}^1 = \text{R}^2 = \text{H}$
c ; $\text{R}^1 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{OMe}$
d ; $\text{R}^1 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{OH}$
e ; $\text{R}^1 = \text{OMe}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{H}$
f ; $\text{R}^1 = \text{NO}_2$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{H}$

cases, and 2'-hydroxychalcones (3) and flavanones (4) were the products (Table 1). We then studied the condensation of 2,5-dihydroxyacetophenone (2a) with benzaldehyde and *p*-anisaldehyde under the same conditions. These reactions, unlike the previous ones, gave 3-arylidene-flavanone as one of the products. Better yields of the 3-arylidene-flavanones (1a and 1b) were, however, obtained by taking greater proportion of aromatic aldehyde and carrying out the condensation in relatively stronger alkaline medium^{5,6} (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ALKALI-CATALYSED CONDENSATION OF 2-HYDROXYACETOPHENONES (2a-e) WITH AROMATIC ALDEHYDES

Reactants* Procedure**	Yield (%) of products†		
	2'-Hydroxy-chalcone(3)	Flavanone(4)	3-Arylidene-flavanone(1)
2b+BD I	62	12	—
2b+AD I	55	15	—
2b+OBD I	60	8	—
2c+BD I	55	10	—
2c+AD I	58	12	—
2c+OBD I	53	10	—
2a+BD I	5	45	15
2a+AD I	trace	20	42
2a+AD II	—	51	18
2a+AD II	—	30	39
2d+BD II	42	20	—
2e+BD II	—	58	—

*BD=Benzaldehyde, AD=*p*-anisaldehyde, OBD=*p*-chlorobenzaldehyde.

**See Experimental.

†Characterised from their melting points and/or spectral (ir and ¹H nmr) data.

6-Hydroxy-3-benzylidene-flavanones (1a) is one of the seven 3-arylidene-flavanones reported by Chawla and Sharma⁸⁻¹⁰. The synthesis of 3-benzylidene-flavanone (1c), 3-(4-methoxybenzylidene)-4'-methoxyflavanone (1d) and 3-(4-chlorobenzylidene)-4'-chloro-7-methoxyflavanone (1e), three more compounds of these authors, was targeted with a view to studying their ¹H nmr spectral features. Attempted condensation of the flavanones (4c-e) with benzaldehyde, *p*-anisaldehyde and *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde respectively, under the alkali-catalysed condition⁸⁻¹⁰ failed to yield these 3-arylidene-flavanones and hence the usual acid-catalysed condition^{7,12} had to be employed. Under the alkaline condition, the starting flavanone mainly isomerised to the corresponding 2'-hydroxychalcone. The melting points of 1c-e prepared by us were found to differ significantly from those reported^{8,9} for these alleged compounds. The ¹H nmr spectra of all the 3-arylidene-flavanones (1a-e) obtained in this study (Table 2) exhibited signals for H-β and H-2 around δ 8.0 and 6.6 respectively, characteristic of *E*-isomers^{7,12}. These protons of *Z*-isomers are reported^{7,12} to appear around δ 6.7 and 6.1 respectively and hence the ¹H nmr spectral data reported by Chawla and Sharma^{8,9} (H-β at δ 6.09-6.37 and H-2 at δ 5.32-5.38) do not at all correspond to those for any isomer of 3-arylidene-flavanones.

Our observation that only *E*-3-arylidene-flavanones are formed during acid-catalysed condensation of flavanones with benzaldehydes corroborated fully the earlier observations^{7,12}. The compounds reported by Chawla and Sharma⁸⁻¹⁰ were alleged to be 3-arylidene-flavanones, two (1a and 1c) of which were identified through alleged synthesis⁹ by the above procedure. The cited ¹H nmr spectral data, however, are inconsistent with either *E*- or *Z*-isomer. The *Z*-isomers are known to be converted to the *E*-isomers with acids⁷ as well as bases¹² and hence the reported⁸⁻¹⁰ compounds formed in

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 3-ARYLIDENEFLAVANONES (1a-e)

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	$\nu_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹	δ (ODCl ₂)*
1a	212-13 (211-14 ^a)	3 390(OH) and 1 670(C=O)	5.51 (1H, br s, OH), 6.60 (1H, br s, H-2), 6.84 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 8.5 Hz, H-7), 7.01 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 8.5 and 2.5 Hz, H-8), 7.24-7.58 (11H, m, ArH), 8.09 (1H, br s, H-β)
1b	201-02	3 320(OH) and 1 670(C=O)	3.73 and 3.80 (each 3H, s, OMe), 5.25 (1H, br s, OH), 6.54 (1H, br s, H-2), 6.65-7.50 (11H, m, ArH), 8.02 (1H, br s, H-β)
1c	104 (104 ^b)	1 670(C=O)	6.65 (1H, br s, H-2), 6.86-7.04 (2H, m, H-6 and H-8), 7.24-7.60 (11H, m, ArH), 7.93 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 8 and 2 Hz, H-5), 8.10 (1H, br s, H-β)
1d	135-36	1 665(C=O)	3.74 and 3.80 (each 9H, s, OMe), 6.61 (1H, br s, H-2), 6.80-7.08 (6H, m, H-6, H-8, H-3', H-5', H-3'' and H-5''), 7.20-7.50 (5H, m, H-7, H-2', H-6', H-2'' and H-6''), 7.94 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 8 and 2 Hz, H-5), 8.04 (1H, br s, H-β)
1e	198-99	1 690(C=O)	3.80 (3H, s, OMe), 6.35 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 2.5 Hz, H-8), 6.49 (1H, br s, H-2), 6.54 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 8.5 and 2.5 Hz, H-6), 7.11-7.45 (8H, m, ArH), 7.87 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 8.5 Hz, H-5), 8.00 (1H, br s, H-β)

*60 MHz machine for 1b and 100 MHz for the others.

^aRef. 5. ^bRef. 7.

alkaline medium are unlikely to be the *Z*-isomers. Furthermore, it is apparent from the given experimental procedure^{8,9} that all the seven 3-arylidene-flavanones obtained by these authors are acidic in nature. But except 1a none of the compounds bears any acidic functionality. Thus, the nature of the compounds reported⁸⁻¹⁰ remains unclear although the authors have adduced analytical and mass spectral evidence⁸⁻¹⁰ also in support of the assigned structures.

The formation of *E*-3-arylidene-flavanones from 2-hydroxyacetophenones and aromatic aldehydes in alkaline medium requires the occurrence of two successive Claisen-Schmidt reactions. The first one, i.e. the formation of 2'-hydroxychalcones, is known with differently substituted 2-hydroxyacetophenones and benzaldehydes¹³, hence the success of the overall reaction depends on the success of the second Claisen-Schmidt reaction. With a view to determining the structural necessity of the 2-hydroxyacetophenone for the occurrence of the second Claisen-Schmidt reaction, we studied the condensation of two more compounds of this class, viz. 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone (2d) and 2-hydroxy-

5-methoxyacetophenone (2e), with benzaldehyde in alkaline medium. But in none of these two cases we could isolate a 3-arylidene flavanone (Table 1). It may therefore be concluded that the ability of 2a to yield *E*-3-arylidene flavanones by condensation with aromatic aldehydes in alkaline medium arises from its 5-OH group. This group being changed to the strongly electron-donating phenolate anion in different intermediates of the overall reaction possibly suppresses the dihydro- γ -pyrone ring opening processes shown in Scheme 1 and thus favours the second Claisen-Schmidt reaction. A 3-OH group in the starting 2-hydroxyacetophenone is also anticipated to behave similarly. In this connection the discussion of the following points appears worthwhile.

(i) Although during condensation with benzaldehyde in alkaline medium 2e failed to generate a 3-arylidene flavanone, it yielded the corresponding flavanone in significantly higher yield compared to the 2-hydroxyacetophenones (2b-d). This is in accordance with previous observation¹⁴ and which leads to the conclusion that 5, the conjugate base of 6-methoxyflavanone, is sufficiently stable against dihydro- γ -pyrone ring opening due to electron-donating effect of its 6-OMe.

(ii) Attempted synthesis of 6-nitro-3-benzylidene flavanone (1f) by condensation of 2-hydroxy-5-nitroacetophenone (2f) with benzaldehyde in alkaline medium was found unsuccessful by Széll and Zarandy¹⁵. The dihydro- γ -pyrone ring opening processes (Scheme 1) would be very much facile in this case and may thus be related to this failure.

R = O[⊖] when started with 2a
R = NO₂ when started with 2f

Scheme 1

(iii) Chromanones having no aryl substituent at 2-position are reported¹⁶ to undergo condensation with aromatic aldehydes in alkaline medium and for this the presence of a 6-/8-OH in the chromanone is not necessary. The condensation becomes feasible possibly because the dihydro- γ -pyrone ring opening processes mentioned above do not become important in this case.

Experimental

Melting points reported are uncorrected. All crystallisations were done from CHCl₃-petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°). The ir spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 297 (nujol) and Perkin-Elmer 597 (KBr) spectrophotometers, and the ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on JEOL FX 100 (100 MHz) and Hitachi R-600 (60 MHz) spectrometers with TMS as internal standard.

2-Hydroxyacetophenones (2a–e): 2a and 2b were prepared by Fries rearrangement of hydroquinone diacetate and phenyl acetate respectively, 2d by Hoesch reaction on resorcinol, and 2c and 2e by partial methylation (Me₂SO₄, K₂CO₃, acetone) of 2d and 2a respectively.

Condensation of 2-hydroxyacetophenones (2a–e) with benzaldehydes in alkaline medium. Procedure I: Condensation reactions of 2-hydroxyacetophenones with aromatic aldehydes were performed according to the conditions reported by Chawla and Sharma^{8,9}. The reaction time was however 72 h in all the cases.

Procedure II: To a solution of the 2-hydroxyacetophenone (0.5 mmol) and aromatic aldehyde (1 mmol) in ethanol (25 ml) 40% KOH (10 ml) was added while cooling in ice. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 72 h and then worked up by acidification with dilute HCl. The crude product mixture was chromatographed over silica gel and the different fractions obtained were crystallised to get the pure products.

Acid-catalysed condensation of flavanones with aromatic aldehydes. Preparation of the *E*-3-arylidene flavanones (1c–e): Through a solution of flavanone (obtained either during condensation of 2-hydroxyacetophenones with aromatic aldehydes in alkaline medium or by acid-catalysed cyclisation¹¹ of 2'-hydroxychalcones) and aromatic aldehyde (1 : 1 mole ratio) in methanol, was passed dry HCl till the solution turned red. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 24 h and then cooled in ice. The resulting solid was washed with cold methanol and then crystallised: 1c, 70%; 1d, 90%; 1e, 45%.

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Added in proof: Very recently it has come to our notice that Krishnamurty *et al.* (H. G. Krishnamurty, B. Prakash and S. Sathyanarayana, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1989, 28, 279) have contradicted one of the papers of Chowla and Sharma.

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